

ABSORPTION OF IODINE BY HYDROXYLAMINE SALTS. PART II. EFFECT OF NEUTRAL SALTS, BASIC SALTS AND ACIDS

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In the presence of either neutral salts, basic salts or acids the iodine absorbed increases rapidly and reaches a maximum in about 2-10 minutes after which iodine appears to be liberated at a higher rate than that at which it is absorbed and hence the apparent absorption of iodine falls. In neutral solution, the liberation of iodine takes place slowly, although as a general rule neutral salts have no appreciable effect on the course of this reaction. The absorption of iodine appears to be fairly rapid and continuously increases with time in the presence of basic salts. In the presence of mineral acids, the primary absorption of iodine is very small, being only about 1/5th of that required in the case of neutral salts. The liberation of iodine in the second stage, under these conditions, is more rapid. In the presence of acetic acid, the absorption is similar to that in the case of neutral salts. The absorption of iodine is slightly more in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide than under ordinary conditions.

In Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 361) it was shown that the quantity of iodine absorbed by hydroxylamine salt solution varied considerably with (i) concentration, (ii) temperature and (iii) time. In this part are recorded the results of a study of the influence of acids, basic salts and neutral salts on the rate and degree of absorption.

EXPERIMENTAL

Effect of Acids on the Course of the Reaction

Mineral Acids.—In the presence of mineral acids the primary absorption of iodine was very small as shown in Table I below. It was almost one fifth of that required in the case of neutral solution (*vide* Table I, Part I) and the liberation of iodine due to secondary reactions was more rapid.

TABLE I

Vol. of *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. solution of hydroxylamine salts at 200 c.c. dilution of 0.02 *N* acid when 25 c.c. of *N*/100 iodine soln. were added every time.

Time.	NH ₂ OH.HCl in HCl M/100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ in H ₂ SO ₄ M/200	NH ₂ OH.HNO ₃ in HNO ₃ M/100	Time.	NH ₂ OH.HCl in HCl M/100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ in H ₂ SO ₄ M/200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ in HNO ₃ M/100
1 min.	1.4 c.c.	1.6 c.c.	1.6 c.c.	10 min.	2.7 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	2.6 c.c.
3	3.4	4.2	3.8	15	—0.8	—0.9	—0.7
5	4.2	5.4	4.4	30	—3.1	—4.5	—6.9

Acetic Acid.—In the presence of acetic acid the absorption was similar to that in the case of neutral solution (see Table I, Part I). The maximum absorption was almost equal to, though a little less, than what occurred in the absence of any other substance as shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Vol. of $N/100$ iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts at 200 c.c. dilution of $0.02 N$ acetic acid when 25 c.c. of $N/100$ iodine soln. were added every time.

Time.	$\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ $M/100$	$(\text{NH}_2\text{OH})_2$ H_2SO_4 $M/200$	NH_2OH HNO_3 $M/100$	Time.	$\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ $M/100$	$(\text{NH}_2\text{OH})_2$ H_2SO_4 $M/200$	NH_2OH HNO_3 $M/100$
1 min.	12.3 c.c.	12.5 c.c.	13.4 c.c.	10 min.	17.0 c.c.	16.9 c.c.	17.4 c.c.
3	16.4	16.4	17.0	15	16.4	16.3	17.1
5	17.3	17.2	17.7	30	14.8	14.6	15.4

Effect of Basic Salts.—The absorption of iodine continually increased with time in the case of basic salts but the basic salts themselves absorbed iodine and it was not possible to differentiate this absorption by basic salts from that of hydroxylamine, though it might be said that in this case the absorption was fairly rapid.

Effect of Neutral Salts.—It may be said as a general rule that neutral salts have no appreciable effect on the course of the reaction as shown in Table III below. The extent of effect on the primary and secondary reactions (Part I, Table I) was, however, almost the same, so that their main effect was to shift the maxima with respect to time. The negative ions: chloride, sulphate and nitrate, behaved similarly *i.e.* they had either no effect on the course of the reaction or the extent of the effect of all the three was the same (Table III). Sodium and potassium ions, however, differ in their effect on the reaction as shown below. The nature and extent of this effect are dependent on the experimental conditions.

TABLE III

Vol of $N/100$ iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts at 200 c.c. dilution of $0.02N$ sodium and potassium salts when 25 c.c. of $N/100$ iodine solution were added every time.

Time.	$M/100\text{-NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ in NaCl .	$M/100\text{-NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ in KCl .	$M/200\text{-(NH}_2\text{OH)}_2$ in Na_2SO_4 .	$M/200\text{-(NH}_2\text{OH)}_2$ in K_2SO_4 .	$M/100\text{-NH}_2\text{OH.HNO}_3$ in NaNO_3 .	$M/100\text{-NH}_2\text{OH.HNO}_3$ in KNO_3 .
1 min.	14.15 c.c.	14.15 c.c.	16.2 c.c.	15.6 c.c.	14.0 c.c.	15.3 c.c.
3	17.05	17.45	18.35	17.35	16.9	17.7
5	17.60	17.80	18.50	17.50	17.2	18.35
10	17.55	17.70	18.45	17.45	17.0	18.20
15	17.40	17.55	18.40	17.40	16.9	18.15
30	16.60	16.75	18.15	17.15	16.3	17.10

Effect of Dilution on the Absorption of Iodine in the presence of Neutral Salts and Acids.—Either in the case of mineral acids or in presence of acetic acid, the quantity of iodine absorbed increased with dilution and tended to be constant at high dilutions as shown in Part I. The only effect of these acids was that the maximum quantity of iodine absorbed was less than that absorbed in neutral solutions, being remarkably less in the presence of mineral acids. In presence of sodium and potassium salts as well, the general behaviour was the same as shown in Part I, Table II. Dilution increased the absorption tending to be constant at high dilutions (*cf.* Part I. Table II).

Effect of the Amount of Iodine on its Absorption in presence of Neutral Salts and Acids.—In the presence of mineral acids, acetic acid, sodium salts and potassium salts, the absorption of iodine increased with the quantity of iodine (concentrated) added tending to be constant when the quantity added was 2 to 3 times more than what was observed to be absorbed in neutral solutions.

Effect of Concentration of Acids on the Absorption of Iodine.—In the presence of mineral acids, iodine was rapidly liberated after a very small initial absorption (Table IV). When the strength of acid was 0.4 *N*, the duration of absorption was apparently so short that no iodine appeared to have been absorbed. The effect of increasing amounts of acetic acid on the absorption of iodine was not so marked as in the case of mineral acids as shown below.

TABLE IV

Vol. of *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts at different concentrations of the acids at 200 c.c. dilution when 25 c.c. of *N*/100 iodine soln. were added every time.

Conc.	<i>M</i> /100-NH ₂ OH.HCl in presence of		<i>M</i> /200-(NH ₂ OH) ₂ .H ₂ SO ₄ in presence of		<i>M</i> /100-NH ₂ OH.HNO ₃ in presence of	
	HCl.	CH ₃ COOH.	H ₂ SO ₄ .	CH ₃ COOH.	HNO ₃ .	CH ₃ COOH.
0.005 <i>N</i>	10.8 c.c.	17.85 c.c.	11.3 c.c.	17.6 c.c.	11.2 c.c.	17.5 c.c.
0.01	7.4	17.65	8.25	17.25	7.7	17.5
0.02	4.2	17.30	5.4	17.25	4.4	17.4
0.05	1.5	17.05	5.25	17.05	1.35	17.2
0.1	0.7	16.55	1.05	16.1	0.3	16.9
0.4	0.0	14.95	0.4	13.8	} Liberates I } from KI	{ 16.25 } 14.3
1.0	..	..	0.15	11.0		

Effect of Concentration of Sodium and Potassium Salts.—Both these ions have an influence on the absorption of iodine. The nature and the extent of this effect are dependent on the experimental conditions (Table V).

TABLE V

Vol. *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts at different concentrations of the neutral salts at 200 c.c. dilution when 25 c.c. of *N*/100 iodine soln. were added every time.

Conc.	<i>M</i> /100-NH ₂ OH.HCl in presence of		<i>M</i> /200-(NH ₂ OH) ₂ .H ₂ SO ₄ in presence of		<i>M</i> /100-NH ₂ OH.HNO ₃ in presence of	
	NaCl.	KCl.	Na ₂ SO ₄ .	K ₂ SO ₄ .	NaNO ₃ .	KNO ₃ .
0.005 <i>M</i>	17.8 c.c.	18.15 c.c.	18.0 c.c.	17.3 c.c.	16.9 c.c.	18.25 c.c.
0.01	17.7	18.0	18.25	17.45	16.95	18.3
0.02	17.6	17.8	18.5	17.5	17.2	18.35
0.05	17.4	17.7	18.4	17.0	17.3	18.35
0.1	17.25	17.65	18.15	17.4	17.35	18.55
0.4	17.1	17.55	..	..	17.4	18.6

Effect of Temperature on the Reaction in the presence of Neutral Salts and Acids.—Either in presence of acids or neutral salts, the rate of absorption of iodine and

the quantity of iodine absorbed increased rapidly as the temperature was raised. The general trend of absorption and reaction are similar to that in the neutral solution as shown in Part I.

Effect of CO₂ on the Absorption of Iodine.—The absorption of iodine was slightly more in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide than in air. This may be due to the fact that the liberation of iodine by secondary reactions is minimised (*cf.* Table VI given below with Table I in Part I).

TABLE VI

Vol. of *N*/100 iodine soln. absorbed at 35° by 5 c.c. soln. of hydroxylamine salts in an atmosphere of CO₂ at 200 c.c. dilution when 25 c.c. of *N*/100 iodine soln. were added every time.

Time.	NH ₂ OH.HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH.HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100	Time.	NH ₂ OH.HCl <i>M</i> /100	(NH ₂ OH) ₂ . H ₂ SO ₄ <i>M</i> /200	NH ₂ OH. HNO ₃ <i>M</i> /100
1 min.	14.4 c.c.	14.4 c.c.	14.5 c.c.	10 min.	17.7 c.c.	17.9 c.c.	17.5 c.c.
3	17.5	17.7	17.4	15	17.2	17.6	17.3
5	18.0	18.1	17.8	30	16.4	16.9	16.7

Experimental details were the same as carried out in Part I. The reaction in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide was carried out by passing a current of CO₂ in the reaction bottles for five minutes.

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